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Digital Knowledge Resources Utilized by Science Teachers

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Abstract

In the 21st century context, there are lots of online resources teachers may use as references and tools in teaching science. These different digital knowledge resources from software to application are very helpful and reliable sources of information for effective teaching of science. This study sought to determine the digital knowledge resources utilized by Science Teachers in different central high schools in Baybay Laguna. Descriptive research design was used in this study and purposive sampling techniques. The respondents of this were the forty-five DepEd science teachers from 6 different central high schools in Baybay Laguna. The study revealed that most of the digital knowledge utilized by DepEd Science Teachers is YouTube. The overall level of acceptability of the science teachers is at the moderate level. Furthermore, the result shows significant relationship in age and position/title of science teachers and digital knowledge resources they utilized. However, there is no significant relationship in terms of gender and grade level handled by the science teachers. There is no significant relationship between respondent's profile and level of acceptability of the digital knowledge resources the results regardless of age, gender, position/title, and grade level handled. This research indicates that a common digital knowledge resource utilized by science teachers is YouTube. This type of digital tool is effective in teaching science since it has a wide variety of tutorials and science discoveries videos that can be used as teaching resources. Teachers regardless of their age must incorporate the use of digital knowledge resources as an effective support tool for learning science.

Keywords: *digital knowledge, science, YouTube, digital tool*

Introduction

Digital technologies include hardware and software which students use at school and at home for educational, social and/or entertainment purposes (Habibi, 2020). Education is viewed as a process for acquiring knowledge and learning. Digital technology has been around for over 50 years with the wide use of the technology for computers and other electronic equipment. In the early 1960s educators and computer scientists began using computers for teaching purposes. Initially, it was used as reading and typing text to provide instructions of how to use the computer due to its low-level interaction with users and later to solve some time consuming problems. However, with the invention of affordable microcomputers and the integration of text, graphics and color there was a rapid spread of computers in business, educational institutes and homes (Alessi & Trollip, 2001). Education methods have been implemented, such as discussion, training, storytelling, teaching, video and assignment.

Resources and digital learning things describe a group of teaching tools that reflect phenomena of science. Such terms apply to animations, simulations web-based or computer-based, games and videos that help, rather than replacing, courses. Even though they are gradually science, used at all grade levels in science classrooms, educators in science have few structures for choosing tools and determining the quality of content and no guidance about how to execute them (Serin & Mart, 2017).

Social media has been shown to be effective for learning. Learners are able to develop higher level thinking skills such as decision making and problem, as well as communicate using social media (Bunus, 2010; Greenhow & Robelia, 2009). In an addition, connections can be made to what they learn in their classrooms (Greenhow & Robelia, 2009). And learning becomes more engaging (Bunus, 2010). Hence, there is a potential for YouTube, as both a video with audio and visual elements, as well as a social media to be used for instructions. Web 2.0 applications such as SNS offer new ways to communicate and transmit information. Junco (2012) states that higher educational staff has an opportunity to help students use Facebook and improve their overall academic experiences improve their overall academic experience. It has been posited that college and university students will soon demand the use of web 2.0 technologies in therefore it is viewed as principal that more research into these technologies should be conducted in order to inform higher education teaching practices and investigate how web 2.0 technologies can be stylized as teaching tools (Hicks & Graber, 2010).

Digital technology supports new teaching pedagogies and learning approaches, which offers high involvement of students, reduce the operational costs and support in retaining the school and university brands and reputations. For instance, technology provides an opportunity to connect with the national or international experts or even lecturers with new schools and universities. This might help in adding the number of courses offered and in turn attracting more students. Due to availability of video-recorded lectures and online access to course materials, a student can connect ubiquitously via any device. This provides greater collaboration between teachers and students and allows them to strengthen their connections with the communities in their respective fields. With this increased availability to students, a teacher is also more empowered to deliver more innovative, exciting lectures along with more personalized feedback and mentoring processes. The emergence of e-learning in the last two decades has brought immense changes in the field of education. This has further led to an important role of social media in education (Central University of Haryana, India 2020).

Teaching science is such a diverse career that it is hard for a teacher to remain up-to-date. A special continuous effort is required for

teachers to learn professionally and become better as science teachers (Showalter, 1984). In order to better prepare students for 21st century science and technology, the latest changes in science teachers is to incorporate technology and research-based teaching into their teaching. As in several countries worldwide, schools closed in Germany in March 2020 and only partially reopened in many as part of the repercussions of the Covid-19 pandemic lockdown. The need to adjust to online teaching was confronted by teachers. In May and June 2020 among early career teachers next we analyzed the degree to which they maintained social relationships.

The degree to which they maintained social interaction with students and mastered key teaching difficulties was examined. The evaluated possible variables are school computer technology, teacher competence such as their technological pedagogical knowledge, and teacher education learning opportunities pertaining to digital teaching and learning. ICT resources, digital teacher competence and teacher education opportunities to gain digital competence are instrumental in adjusting to online teaching during school closures at COVID-19. For these problems with technology in the classroom, teachers must provide flexible solutions, keeping students involved, challenged and healthy while eliminating the need for teachers to stand over students as they work and allowing you to concentrate on what matters most. A lack of awareness and comprehension of how to use technology, or frustration with using it is another common challenge for teachers trying to incorporate technology into their classrooms. Teachers who have these issues often fail to be provided with tools for professional development to help the skills and familiarity to efficiently and effectively implement technology. The teacher curriculum provides comprehensive training about how teachers can best use the program in their classroom to promote digital learning.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the digital learning resources of Science teachers for learners particularly to Public Secondary High Schools from San Juan National High School to Santa Maria Integrated High School. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following question:

1. What is the profile of the Science Teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. position/title; and
 - 1.4. grade level handled?
2. What are the digital knowledge resources utilized by Science teachers?
3. What is the level of acceptability of the science teachers on the utilized digital knowledge resources?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile and digital knowledge resources utilized by Science teachers?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the profile and the acceptability of the digital knowledge resources utilized by Science teachers?

Methodology

Research Design

The study assessed the digital knowledge resources utilized by science teachers from San Juan National High School to Santa Maria Integrated National High School, Laguna. This study use the survey method of research.

In the survey research, respondents answer through surveys or questionnaires or polls. They are a popular market research tool to collect feedback from respondents. A study to gather useful data should have the right survey questions.

A survey is a data collection tool that lists a set of structured questions to which respondents provide answers based on their knowledge and experiences. It is a standard data gathering process that allows you to access information from a predefined group of respondents during research.

Respondents

This study was focused on the experiences of the teachers from San Juan National High School to Santa Maria Integrated High School, Laguna who experience the digital knowledge resources utilized by science teachers. All secondary high school majors in science participated in the study.

In this study, the researcher uses the purposive sampling. The science teachers from San Juan National High School to Santa Maria Integrated High School were selected.

The respondents were selected purposively. A purposive sample is a non-probability sample, often known as selected, interview, when deciding who to ask to respondents, this approach relies on the researcher's judgment. Thus, researchers may interview a "representative" sample that matches their preferences, or target individuals with certain characteristics.

Instrument

The instruments that the researcher uses in collecting data for the study are survey questionnaires that aim to determine the digital

knowledge resources utilized by Science Teachers.

A survey questionnaire with a total of 20 items will be used as an instrument in this study to determine the digital knowledge resources utilized by Science teachers in High School Teachers.

The researcher will distribute the questionnaires all science teachers ask to read the statements given and choose their answer based on the 4- Likert Scale range from 4= Highly Acceptable, 3= Moderately Acceptable, 2= Slightly Acceptable, 1= Not Acceptable and Section A is all about determining the different digital knowledge resources for teachers in utilized digital knowledge resources on teaching. The section B is all about the digital knowledge resources utilized by science teachers in teaching knowledge resources as instruction.

Procedure

This study has undertaken a certain procedure to accomplish the study. The researcher consulted his adviser and panels to enhance the research instrument so that the needed data would be gathered accurately.

Descriptive research was used in this study. It aims at defining a population, condition or phenomenon accurately and systematically. It can answer questions about what, where, when and how, but not questions about why. to analyze one or more variables, a descriptive research method. Unlike in experimental studies, any of the variables are not monitored or manipulated by the investigator, but only observes and measures those (McCombes, 2019).

The researcher personally asked for the permission of the principal of participating secondary school. Gathering the number of science teachers in their department followed then formally asked the science teachers to become participants for this study. The survey instrument was administered to the respondents via google form to answer the prepared questionnaire. Due to the pandemic, face-to-face transaction is not possible. After answering the questions, the researchers collected and statistically analyzed, tabulated, and interpreted all the gathered data.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered with the aim of determining the digital knowledge resources utilized by science teachers from San Juan National High School to Santa-Maria Integrated National High School.

Profile of the Teacher-Respondents

Table 1 shows that 31% or 14 of the total respondents are within the age range from 40-49 years old, 67% are female. Most of these teachers have a position of Teacher III (38%), Teacher II (22%) and Teacher I (36%) handling grade 8 and grade 10 with the percentage of 29%.

According to Renne Hobbs (2017), digital learning motivation profiles suggest unique identity perspectives among Turkish science, language arts, and information and communication technology (ICT) teachers. Among the most frequent identification positions are "Techie," "Demystifier," and "Tastemaker." Teachers' subject-area specialization and digital learning motivation profiles were revealed to be statistically significant. Teachers' digital learning motivation profiles should be evaluated and learning experiences should be based on the strengths of teachers' ideas and the most significant conceptual themes to them.

Table 1. *Profile of the respondents*

Age	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
29 and under	10	22%	3
30-39	11	24%	2
40-49	14	31%	1
50-59	9	20%	4
60-69	1	2%	5
Total	45	100%	
Gender			
Male	15	33%	2
Female	30	67%	1
Total	45	100%	
Position/Title			
MT-I	1	2%	4.5
MT-II	1	2%	4.5
T-I	16	36%	2
T-II	10	22%	3
T-III	17	38%	1
Total	45	100%	

Grade level handled			
Grade 7	10	22%	4
Grade 8	13	29%	1.5
Grade 9	8	18%	5
Grade 10	13	29%	1.5
Grade 11	11	24%	3
Grade 12	6	13%	6

Digital Knowledge Resources Utilized by Science Teachers

Table 2 shows that the digital knowledge resources utilized by science teachers among the list, YouTube is on top rank with 91%. Digitalization is influencing the current generation of students. Educators are becoming increasingly aware of and adapting new instructional methods because of digitalization. YouTube is leading the way as a result of digitization. The title of most versatile medium for content transactions in the world both inside and outside the classroom, YouTube video is interesting media which gives the students better exposure. Moreover, some previous studies have proved that using YouTube videos can enhance students' skill, followed by Google with 87%. Google Classroom is a free application that allows students and teachers to connect, collaborate, organize, and create assignments without using paper. Google Classroom is a digital tool that is only available to Google Apps for education users (GAFE). This is a free collaboration toolkit that comprises web applications such as Google Docs, Google Drive, Gmail, and others.

Google Classroom Advantages are: 1. Enables lecturers to publish lesson notes and generate announcements, and set deadlines for assignments. 2. Teachers can combine several groups into one. Then assign each group a separate task As a result, the class will be more active and engaged. interesting. 3. Teachers can quickly detect kids who are absent from class. students who submit their assignments late. 4. It is adaptable, allowing teachers to extend due dates as needed. That all students can turn in their homework, it also allows teachers to update or revise their lessons. 5. Teachers' previous posts can be reused and the message was then sent to the same or a different group. 6. Teachers can be added to the classroom as well. Can also grade assignments for students, respectively.

Facebook with 78% on the contrary, flicker and twitter were the least. Both have 0 frequencies, therefore with 0% percentage. According to Saban and Aslihan (2020), one of the social media technologies that has become a part of our life is YouTube. It is used as an instructional tool by many educators. Finding out what students think about YouTube and how they feel about it can help them make better use of it. Metaphors and attitudes of secondary school students about YouTube were investigated for this aim.

Pecay and Kayee (2017) included in their study that in today's digital age, YouTube is one of the most prominent social networking networks. Along with its growing popularity and the demand to incorporate ICT into the curriculum, YouTube's plethora of benefits for improving science education urges science teachers to use it in the classroom. This inquiry was then carried out in order to gain a better understanding of how and why science teachers use YouTube in their classes.

Table 2. *Digital Knowledge resources utilized by Science teachers*

<i>Digital knowledge resources</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
You Tube	41	91%	1
Electronic Library	5	11%	6
Facebook	35	78%	3
Educational Facebook Pages	23	51%	4
Google	39	87%	2
Skype	1	2%	7
Flicker	0	0%	8.5
Yahoo	9	20%	5
Twitter	0	0%	8.5
Digital knowledge resources use the most			
You Tube	42	93%	1
Electronic Library	2	4%	5
Facebook	31	69%	3
Educational Facebook Pages	13	29%	4
Google	41	91%	2
Skype	1	2%	6.5
Flicker	0	0%	8.5
Yahoo	1	2%	6.5
Twitter	0	0%	8.5

Level of Acceptability of Science Teachers on the Utilized Digital Knowledge Resources

Table 3 shows that the teachers highly accept the use of Digital Knowledge Resources with weighted mean of 3.51. However, in terms of overall level of acceptability the result shows that respondents moderately accept the use of Digital Knowledge Resources specifically on its creative utilization, reinforcing introduced concepts, classroom context fitting. In addition, DKR are moderately acceptable due to the concern in the teacher-student relationship inside the classroom, time management and DKR utilization skills.

Further, although the teachers utilize different online networking sites such as Facebook, Google, and YouTube very frequently particularly in their participation in district or school- provided professional development on using digital resources in the classroom, their frequency of utilization is generally moderate. The different DKR are moderately used in online tutorials, meeting the specific learning needs of students, introducing new concepts or topics.

According to Ondiegi (2014), though schools with digital learning resources have not optimized the use of ICT, e-learning resources such as the internet and laptops can help improve learners' educational outcomes. Learner attitude, competency, usefulness, and acceptability of ICT tools are all impediments to ICT use, according to the study. Integration and additional workload on the learners, as well as a lack of necessary resources such as internet, laptops or tablets, and electricity, are all impediments to ICT use. In the 1980s, information and communication technology (ICT) took over from computers. This marked a significant change in the ability to store and retrieve data. The email provided a secure means of communicating with the general public.

Table 3. *Level of acceptability of Science teachers on the utilized digital knowledge resources in terms of Experiences in using Digital Knowledge Resources*

EXPERIENCES IN USING DIGITAL KNOWLEDGE RESOURCES	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. I am concerned about how to use digital resources creatively.	3.49	Moderately Acceptable	2
2. I often edit digital resources to fit my specific classroom context.	3.27	Moderately Acceptable	4
3. I like using digital resources.	3.51	Highly Acceptable	1
4. I am concerned about how using digital resources might change my relationship with students.	3.16	Moderately Acceptable	5
5. I have trouble finding the right digital resources to use.	2.4	Slightly Acceptable	10
6. I use digital resources to reinforce concepts that I've already introduced.	3.38	Moderately Acceptable	3
7. I often have technical problems with my computer when I try to use digital resources.	2.47	Slightly Acceptable	9
8. I often have technical problems in connectivity when I try to use digital resources.	2.67	Moderately Acceptable	8
9. I usually have enough time to plan lessons using digital resources.	3.04	Moderately Acceptable	7
10. I am skilled at using technology tools to access digital content.	3.09	Moderately Acceptable	6
General Weighted Mean	3.05	Moderately Acceptable	

Table 4. *Level of acceptability of Science teachers on the utilized digital knowledge resources in terms of Frequency of Utilization*

Frequency of Utilization	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. I use online tutorials to learn more about digital resources.	3.02	Moderately Frequent	9
2. I use online networking sites (i.e. Facebook, Google, YouTube, etc.) to find digital resources.	3.71	Very Frequent	1
3. I adopt digital resources to meet the specific learning needs of my students	3.47	Moderately Frequent	3.5
4. I use online digital libraries to search for digital resources.	2.91	Slightly Frequent	10

5. I use digital resources to introduce new concepts or topics.	3.38	Moderately Frequent	6
6. I use digital resources in my personal life outside the classroom.	3.47	Moderately Frequent	3.5
7. I use a teacher – directed approach to classroom instruction.	3.24	Moderately Frequent	7
8. I participate in district or school-provided professional development on using digital resources in the classroom.	3.69	Very Frequent	2
9. I get online to watch pre-recorded presentations or talks about digital resources.	3.4	Moderately Frequent	8
10. I participate in online (webinars) about digital resources.	3.44	Moderately Frequent	5
General Weighted Mean	3.37	Moderately Frequent	

Relationship between the Profile and Digital Knowledge Resources Utilized by Science Teachers

Table 4 shows the results between experiences in using digital knowledge resources and the respondent’s profile. The age has a p-value of 0.05 which is below the alpha level of significance, therefore significant relationships exist. However, gender has p-value of 0.36, position/title has p-value 0.15 and grade level handled has p-value of 0.45. These are above the alpha level of significance so the verbal interpretations in terms of relationship are not significant. This implies that age is associated with the utilization of DKR of Science teachers.

Table 4. Relationship Between the Profile and Digital Knowledge Resources Utilized by Science Teachers

Profile	Chi-square	p-value	Relationship
Age	24. 015	0.05	Significant
Gender	3. 53	0.36	Not Significant
Position/Title	20. 86	0.15	Not Significant
Grade level handled	15. 06	0.45	Not Significant

Relationship Between the Profile and Acceptability of the Digital Knowledge Resources Utilized by Science Teachers

Table 5 shows the results between experiences in using digital knowledge resources and the respondent’s profile. The age has a p-value of 0.05185 which is below the alpha level of significance, therefore significant relationships exist. However, gender has p-value of 0.49785, position/title has p-value 0.4908 and grade level handled has p-value of 0.1733. These are above the alpha level of significance so the verbal interpretations in terms of relationship are not significant.

Table 5. Experiences and frequency of using Digital Knowledge Resources

Profile	t/f – value	p-value	Experience	Frequency of Utilization
Age	4. 15	0.05185	Significant	Not Significant
Gender	-0.525	0.49785	Not Significant	Not Significant
Position/Title	1.29	0.4908	Not Significant	Not Significant
Grade level handled	1.64	0.1733	Not Significant	Not Significant

According to Karaoglan and Kisa (2009), integration of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) into education has been an important concern in many countries. Recently, the Turkish Ministry of Education has also made great efforts and major financial investments to implement ICT into teaching and learning environments. However, as in many developing countries, ICT tools are

provided to teachers without considering their attitudes toward ICT. The purpose of this study was to reveal Turkish primary and secondary science teachers' attitudes toward ICT in education and then explore the relationship between teachers' attitudes and factors which are related to teachers' personal characteristics (gender, age, computer ownership at home, and computer experience)

Conclusions

The study examined the Digital Knowledge Resources utilized by Science Teachers and it shows that YouTube is the most common Digital Knowledge Resource widely used by Science Teachers in 6 secondary schools in Baybay Laguna. The study also test the relationship between the profile and digital knowledge resources utilized by Science teachers and has come to the conclusion that in terms of age and position/title of the science teacher have interconnection to Digital Knowledge Resources utilized by Science Teachers.

Therefore, indicates that age of the Science Teachers is related on their chosen digital knowledge resources. However, in terms of gender and grade level handled by Science Teachers have nothing to do with their chosen Digital Knowledge Resources. In terms of relationship between the relationship between the profile and the acceptability of the digital knowledge resources utilized by Science teachers, there is no significant relationship between the two variables. Therefore, regardless of the respondents' profile it is not interrelated to the level of acceptability of Digital Knowledge Resources utilized by Science Teachers.

This study contributes to exploring ideas about what Digital Knowledge Resources used by Science Teachers. This study also opens up the idea for future research possibilities. However, one of the weaknesses of this research study is the small range of locality of the study. A wide locality of schools and a large number of respondents is recommended to validate the findings presented in this study.

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